

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF THE COURSE OF PEPTIC ULCER OF THE STOMACH AND DUODENUM IN COMBINATION WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES ON THE STATE OF LIFE OF THE PATIENT

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Abstract

The article presents a decrease in the quality of life (mental and physical health) in patients with peptic ulcer disease of the stomach and duodenum, which is aggravated by the presence of *H. pylori* infection genes and concomitant diseases, type 2 diabetes.

Gastric ulcer is a pathological process that is manifested by the formation of deep epithelial defects in the mucous membrane of the organ, which reach up to the muscle layer. This pathology is common among gastroenterology patients and accounts for approximately 10% of all those who sought consultation and treatment from a gastroenterologist.

Conclusion. In the presence of both genes, internal tension and constant anxiety are observed in patients with PVS and PDK, the manifestation of the disease indicates deterioration of quality of life and psychological indicators of anxiety. And the presence of two toxigenic strains of *Helicobacter* infection in combination with T2DM aggravates the condition of patients with PVS and PD and worsens the quality of life.

Keywords: gastric, ulcer, diabetes, H.P.

Relevance of the topic. Gastric ulcer is a pathological process that is manifested by the formation of deep epithelial defects in the mucous membrane of the organ, which reach up to the muscle layer. This pathology is common among gastroenterology patients and accounts for approximately 10% of all those who sought consultation and treatment from a gastroenterologist. Ulcer disease tends to be chronic, but acute ulcers also occur, which poses a direct threat to health, and not only because of the risk of bleeding.

The main reasons for the development of a stomach ulcer:

- infection with *Helicobacter pylori* (NR) (microorganisms settle in the stomach and destroy the protective surface layer of the epithelium with their vital activity);
- stress (blood circulation of the mucous membrane is disrupted, blood vessels spasm and the mechanism of synthesis of protective mucus is disrupted);
- alcohol (ethanol increases the synthesis of gastric juice, hydrochloric acid);
- diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, for example - intestinal dyskinesia, erosive gastritis;
- preservation, pickled and fermented products - acetic or acetylsalicylic acid is often added to them, which increases the aggressiveness of gastric juice;
- intoxication with nitrates, dyes and varnishes (when inhaling the vapors of these substances,

nitrogenous compounds enter the blood and create conditions for H.R. activity);

- change of climate, time zone (this is a kind of stress for the body, weakening of immunity and a reason for the development or exacerbation of HCV);
- immune disorders, foci of chronic infection (long-term mild inflammation in the body weakens the activity of gastric cells that synthesize mucus);
- the use of certain drugs (in the presence of autoimmune processes and cardiovascular diseases, hormones and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) must be used, which impair the ability of the epithelium to resist hydrochloric acid and *Helicobacter* infection).

It is known that H.R. is one of the main links of pathogenesis. Recently, there have been reports of innate and acquired immune protection of the host organism, which together with the factors of the stomach environment stimulate a high rate of genomic variability of H.R. [1,2], which contributes to the active evolution of the pathogen and its adaptation to its host. The increased virulence of H.R., determined by the genes *cagA* and *vacA*, leads to the development of the most serious diseases of the stomach and PPD: atrophic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and stomach cancer [3].

The purpose of the work: to evaluate the quality of life of patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with arterial hypertension and type 2 diabetes in the presence of toxigenic strains.

Research materials and methods. 28 patients with PVS and PDK with the presence of genes

cagA+vacA+ HP (1st group), 20 patients with PVS and PDK due to the presence of genes cagA+ and vacA+ (2nd group), 22 patients with PVS and PDK based on the presence of cagA genes were examined +vacA+ in combination with T2DM (3rd group), 38 patients with PVS and PDK according to the presence of strains cagA+ or vacA+ in combination with T2DM (4th group) and 30 PZO (5th group). With the help of the SF-36 questionnaire, we assessed the mental and physical health of the examinees.

All patients received inpatient treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital and the Chernivtsi Regional Endocrinology Center in 2013-2016.

The presence of PVS and DPC was verified on the basis of the clinical picture, anamnesis data, objective methods of examining the patient, the results of endoscopic and morphological studies of SOS and DPC.

To assess the patients' complaints and the results of the objective examination, we used the indicator of average degree of severity (SST). To calculate this indicator, the intensity of pain and other manifestations of combined pathology was first assessed according to the scale: 0 points — no complaints; 1 point — complaints are minimal; 2 points — complaints are moderate; 3 points — complaints are pronounced or very pronounced. After that, SST was calculated according to formula 2.1:

$$CST=(a+2b+3c)/(a+b+c+d) \quad (2.1)$$

where SST is the average degree of severity of clinical manifestations; a - the number of patients with symptom severity of 1 point; b - the number of patients with symptom severity of 2 points; c - the number of patients with symptom severity of 3 points; d - the number of patients with no symptom.

To verify the diagnosis of PV of the stomach and duodenum, fibrogastroduodenoscopy was performed using the "GIF Q-40" device of the Olympus company (Japan) with targeted biopsy according to the generally accepted methodology. *H. pylori* DNA was isolated from CO biopsies from the antral part of the stomach using special kits for DNA isolation ("Litekh". South Russia). *H. pylori* cagA and vacA genes in biopsies were determined using Helikopol reagent kits (Litekh, Russia). The assessment of detection of *H. pylori* cagA and vacA genes and their alleles was carried out according to the instructions, namely the presence of a DNA fragment of the cagA gene of 404 bp. light filter and vacA (alleles s1+s2, m1, m2) on 259 bp. +286 p.n., 290 p.n. and 352 p.n. in accordance.

Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS Statistics 17 Multilanguage program. In the process of statistical processing of the research results, the type of data distribution, descriptive indicators, the probability of the obtained results and other types of analysis were determined. For data corresponding to a normal distribution, the arithmetic mean of the sample (M), standard error (m), maximum and minimum values were determined. The results were calculated using parametric and non-parametric research methods (Student coefficient (p), Pearson coefficient (χ^2), confidence interval (CI), Pearson correlation

coefficient (r)). The probabilities of the difference between the obtained data were estimated by the Student's coefficient (t). A difference of $p < 0.05$ was considered probable.

The results of own research. In patients with PVS and PD, the presence of the sagA+vacA+ genotype occurred in 17 people (51.51%) and 11 people (55%), the sagA+vacA- genotype - in 4 people (12.12%) and 1 person (5%), of the sagA-vacA+ genotype - in 9 people (27.28%) and in 6 people (30%), respectively. The combination of cagA-/vacA- genes was observed in 3 people (9.09%) and in 2 people (10%), respectively. Therefore, only the difference in the prevalence of the cagA+vacA- genotype was significant, which was 2.4 times more prevalent in patients with PVDPC than in PVS.

When assessing physical health, differences in general health (GH) were found in patients with PVS and DPK, taking into account the toxigenicity of strains of H.P. and accompanying pathology. With the presence of genes cagA+vacA+ in patients with PVS and PDK, there is a decrease in physical activity by 38.91%, physical-role activity by 27.85%, social activity by 43.53%, and emotional-role activity by 11.32%. In the presence of genes cagA+vacA+ in patients with PVS and PD in combination with T2DM, more significant differences are noted (decrease in physical activity by 48.87%, physical-role activity by 39.55%, social activity by 48.75%, emotional- role activity by 23.57%). In the group of patients with the presence of cagA+vacA-/cagA-vacA+ genes, these health indicators changed slightly. In general, the state of somatic health indicated insufficient ability to perform everyday physical activities.

Evaluating the mental status, it was found that there was a greater decrease in patients with PVS and PDK in combination with T2DM, namely, in the presence of genes cagA+vacA-/cagA-vacA+ by 16.4% and in the presence of cagA+vacA+ - by 33.56%. Against the background of impairment of mental health, social and physical activity, general health decreases (in the group of patients with PVS and PDK cagA+vacA+ by 30.37%, cagA+vacA-/cagA-vacA+ - by 22.03%, in the group of patients with PVS and DPC in combination with T2DM, cagA+vacA+ by 39.04%, cagA+vacA-/cagA-vacA+ - by 27.98%).

Conclusion. Thus, in the presence of both genes, patients with PVS and PDK have internal tension, constant anxiety, the manifestation of the disease indicates deterioration of quality of life and psychological indicators of anxiety. And the presence of two toxigenic strains of helicobacter infection in combination with T2DM aggravates the condition of patients with PVS and DPC and worsens the quality of life.

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